

None of the insecticides retarded seedling growth at the tested doses. Chlorpyrifos, disulfoton, monocrotophos, endosulfan, and basudin favored seedling growth. Of the granular formulations, phorate at 12.5, 10.0, and 7.5 kg a.i./kg seed per hectare was effective against the pest both in initial and residual toxicities; it was closely followed by chlorfenvinphos and disulfoton at 12.5

kg a.i. Next in order of effectiveness were chlorfenvinphos and disulfoton at 10.0 kg a.i., fenthion at 12.5 and 10.0 kg a.i., and quinalphos and chlorpyrifos at 12.5 kg a.i. Among the foliar sprays, carbofuran at concentrations of 0.1% and 0.075% was superior. Monocrotophos was next in effectiveness.

It was concluded that a single application of phorate at 7.5 kg a.i./350

kg seed per hectare, applied along with rice seed, can keep it free of the adult *D. armigera* throughout the nursery period. Carbofuran at 0.1% is the choice among foliar sprays. The granules were tried at high levels to check for adverse effect on the seedlings. Very low levels of 1 to 1.5 kg ai. were also found effective.

Residues of phorate-gamma BHC and mephosfolan in Jaya grain and straw

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Granular insecticides, introduced on a large scale in India during 1967 and 1968 have become popular with Indian farmers. Following application, translocation may result in retention of small quantities of poisons or their metabolites in the plant tissue. In view of the possible health hazard, it is imperative to analyze quantitatively the residue to find out if it is below or above the tolerance limit.

Two recently introduced granular insecticides, phorate-gamma BHC — Paddigard 7.5 G, containing 5% phorate (thimet) plus 2.5% BHC — and

mephosfolan (Cytrolane 5 G), were tested during boro (summer season) to determine the residues in the grain and straw of Jaya.

Table 2. Cytrolane residue^a in Jaya rice grain and straw.

Treatment	Cytrolane (ppm)	
	Grain	Straw
Cytrolane 5 G 0.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.03	0.13
Cytrolane 5 G 0.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.06	0.36
Cytrolane 5 G 1.0 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.06	0.13
Cytrolane 5 G 1.0 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.04	0.28
Control	0.04	0.01

^aMean of 3 replicates.
DT = days after transplanting.

Table 1. Phorate and gamma BHC residues^a in Jaya rice grain and straw, Burdwan, India.

Treatment	Phorate (ppm)	Phorate oxygen analogue sulphone (ppm)	Phorate oxygen analogue (ppm)	Phorate sulphone (ppm)	Gamma BHC (ppm)
<i>Grain</i>					
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT ^b	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
Control (grain)	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
<i>Straw</i>					
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.06
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.06
Control (straw)	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.06

^aMean of 3 replicates. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

Each of the seven treatments was replicated three times in the experimental plots in Burdwan, India. Impounded water was maintained at a depth of about 4 cm during the vegetative and reproductive phases. The soil was fine loamy (clay loam). After harvest, random samples of rice and straw were airshipped to the ACCO Product Development Laboratory, Europe-African Region, Gosport, England, for gas-liquid chromatographic assay. The results are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests

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The intensification of farming practices, deforestation, indiscriminate use of pesticides (especially broad-spectrum and persistent ones) and a consequent decline in population of natural enemies of insects, and other disrupting forces in the ecosystem have accentuated the problem of insect pests on rice, particularly in the warm and humid tropics. Generally the nontolerant high-yielding rice varieties (HYV) suffer most from insect damage, especially during kharif (wet season) when the main rice crop is grown. Low yield associated with the kharif crop may be one reason for limited use of HW during that season.

An "Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests," drawn up by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, started to function during kharif 1975 in the pest-prone area of Pandua, Bengal. Its principal objectives are 1) to determine why only about 15